

VALORIZATION OF POST-CONSUMER BIODEGRADABLE POLYMER BLEND TO CREATE COMPOSITES WITH AGRO-INDUSTRIAL BY-PRODUCTS AS REINFORCING FILLERS

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Keywords: Biodegradable Polymers, Mechanical Recycling, Biocomposites, Natural Fibers, Thermomechanical Properties

ABSTRACT

This work explores the influence of multiple reprocessing cycles and the incorporation of natural fillers on the properties of a post-consumer biodegradable polymer blend composed mainly of PLA and PBS. The blend, originally used for the production of single-use cutlery, was subjected to up to eight extrusion/injection molding cycles to simulate mechanical recycling and to evaluate thermal, morphological, and mechanical stability. The results demonstrate that reprocessing does not significantly affect the mechanical properties of the blend, likely due to the stabilizing effect of the inorganic filler. A slight decrease in the PLA degradation peak was observed via TGA analysis, from 346.6 °C (Ext 1) to 343.3 °C (Ext 8), attributable to thermo-mechanical degradation phenomena such as chain scission. The incorporation of agro-industrial residues, such as wheat and rice straw (10 wt.%), enhanced both the tensile and flexural moduli of the composites. However, the presence of these natural reinforcements resulted in a slight reduction in both the onset degradation temperature and the PLA degradation peak, with decreases of 1.5% and 5.8% for wheat straw, and 3.4% and 5.5% for rice straw, respectively. These findings demonstrate that biodegradable blends can be recycled through multiple mechanical processing cycles without significant loss of performance. Furthermore, the integration of natural lignocellulosic fillers offers an effective solution to enhance mechanical properties while reducing reliance on virgin polymer content. This approach supports the development of sustainable and cost-effective composite materials aligned with circular economy principles.

1 INTRODUCTION

Originally designed as a symbol of technological progress, fuel-based plastics have revolutionized the modern world by making human life easier [1] thanks to their versatility, low weight, durability and low production costs [2]. The first plastics were introduced in the 1920s and production expanded in following years [3]. In 1965, the yearly production was about 15 million tons (Mt) and increased to 360

million tons (Mt) in 2018 [4]. As a result, the global annual production of plastics has continuously grown since their initial development. However, the use of plastic has created serious environmental problems due to their inability to undergo biological degradation and aging, leading to pollution and persistence in the environment for many years after disposal [5, 6]. This has caused large amounts of waste to accumulate in landfills or in natural environment [7]. Furthermore, the production processes of synthetic polymers, such as ethylene or propylene, require the use of harmful compounds and result in the formation of toxic by-products [8]. This has prompted the need to find alternatives to fossil-based polymers. In recent years, biodegradable polymers produced from natural raw materials, such as cellulose, starch and chitosan [6] have been introduced to the market. These materials are capable of biodegrading. Compared to petroleum-based polymers, they are more compatible with the principles of the circular economy, making them a preferred choice. Bioplastic production has grown significantly in recent years, rising from 2.4 million tons (Mt) in 2021 to an estimated 7.5 million tons (Mt) by 2026 [9]. The use of these polymers could represent a solution to plastic accumulation at the end of their life cycle, thanks to their ability to degrade through biological processes involving microorganisms capable of breaking the polymer chains [10]. However, biodegradation requires specific environmental conditions to occur, such as oxygen concentration, moisture, temperature [10, 11, 12], as well as a concentration of microorganisms, which play a crucial role in determining both the rate and degree of biodegradation, making it an inadequate rapid solution for waste disposal. Furthermore, although biodegradable polymers are often promoted as environmentally friendly alternatives to conventional plastics, their degradation is typically limited to controlled industrial composting facilities. Under natural environmental conditions, such as soil or marine ecosystems, the specific parameters required for biodegradation (temperature, humidity, oxygen levels, and microbial activity) are often not met. As a result, these materials may persist in the environment for extended periods, raising concerns about their actual end-of-life sustainability and environmental impact [13]. In addition, biodegradable polymers, as polylactic acid (PLA), polybutylene succinate (PBS) and poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) are more expensive than fossil-based polymers [14, 15].

Various strategies have been proposed to solve this issue, such as mechanical and chemical recycling, as well as incineration [16]. Chemical recycling involves solvolysis, pyrolysis, or hydrolysis reactions that break down the polymer chain into monomeric units and the recovered material can be repolymerized an indefinite number of times to produce the corresponding biopolymers [16]. On the other hand, it is the most expensive method due to the large amount of energy required to reach the temperature needed for the reaction to take place such as depolymerization [17]. Meanwhile incineration is able to produce energy but, besides being high-cost, could produce unsafe exhaust gases [18]. Mechanical recycling could be the most efficient solution to reduce landfill waste because it is cost-effective and without significant alteration in the chemical structure of materials [11, 19, 20]. Nevertheless, repeated mechanical reprocessing can lead to thermo-mechanical degradation phenomena, such as chain scission, resulting in mechanical property losses. Investigating the extent of these effects and how to mitigate them is essential for designing sustainable circular solutions. The use of agro-waste products can also be a viable solution to reduce landfill waste, as they often originate as residues from crop cultivation and agro-industrial operations. Materials such as rice straw, wheat straw, and coconut shells are renewable, abundantly available, and contribute to preserving the bio-based and biodegradable nature of the final product [21]. The incorporation of natural lignocellulosic fillers has gained significant attention as a strategy to enhance the stiffness, reduce polymer consumption, and improve the sustainability of the final bio-based polymer composites [22]. Recent studies have shown that combining mechanical recycling with the addition of natural fibers can not only recover post-consumer polymer waste but also improve or stabilize the mechanical properties of degraded polymers through fiber reinforcement [23]. The present study aims to evaluate the effect of reprocessing on a commercial post-consumer biodegradable polymer blend, as well as the influence of incorporating natural fillers derived from agricultural waste. This investigation addresses the performance evolution across multiple recycling cycles and assesses the feasibility of valorizing agro-waste as reinforcing fillers in bio-based composites.

The blend was reprocessed through eight cycles of extrusion and injection molding. The blend, used for the production of single-use cutlery, is PLA-based with PBS and inorganic filler. Mechanical properties were studied through tensile and three-point bending tests. Thermal properties were evaluated by

thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry analysis (DSC), meanwhile thermo-mechanical tests as Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT) and Vicat (VST) were conducted. The effect of adding 10 wt.% of wheat straw (WS) and rice straw (RS) to the reprocessed blend was also investigated in terms of mechanical and thermal characterization of the final composite. Fracture surface analyses of the reprocessed polymer and the natural fiber composites were performed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to assess morphological changes and filler dispersion. Potential effects on the blend compostability after subsequent mechanical reprocessing were evaluated through aerobic tests in controlled composting conditions.

2 MATERIALS

Disposable cutlery, including knives and forks, was crushed into pellets. The material was dried at 60 °C for 1 day before the extrusion (corotating twin-screw extruder, Thermo Scientific Process 11, ThermoFisher Scientific)/injection molding (Haake MiniJet IPro, Thermo Fisher Scientific) reprocessing cycles. The rotational speed was set at 150 rpm and the following temperature profile was used from zone 1 to 8: 160 °C-165 °C-170 °C-170 °C-175 °C-180 °C-185 °C-180 °C. During the injection molding, the mold and the cylinder were maintained at 70 °C and 180 °C, respectively. To reproduce several reprocessing cycles, the polymer was pelletized after each injection and subjected to successive extrusion/injection cycles, up to eight times. The resulting samples were denoted as “Ext n”, where n represents the number of extrusion/injection cycles. Rice straw (RS) was supplied by Azienda Riso Milano (Italy), while wheat straw (WS) was obtained from Agriturismo Cascina Scanna (Italy). Both RS and WS were washed with tap-water and dried at 60 °C for 24 h. In the final stage, the materials were milled using a knife mill. To recover the inorganic filler, the polymer was dissolved using chloroform.

3 METHODS

Tensile and flexural tests were conducted with a Zwick/Roell Z010 universal testing machine. Tensile tests were conducted in displacement control with a 10 mm/min crosshead speed at room temperature according to ISO 527-2 (type 1BA, $L_0 = 30$ mm) using dog-bone specimens with a thickness of 1.5 mm and a width of 5 mm. Flexural properties were measured through three-point bending tests according to ISO 178. The crosshead speed was set at 5 mm/min and the sample dimensions were 80 × 10 × 4 mm. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted from room temperature to 800 °C in nitrogen atmosphere using a heating ramp of 10 °C/min (TG209 F1 Libra by Netzsch). Differential scanning calorimetry analysis (DSC) was performed using DSC 214 Polyma by Netzsch under a nitrogen flow of 60 mL/min, following this thermal program: first heating from -40 °C to 200 °C (5 min hold interval), cooling to -40 °C (5 min hold interval) and second heating to 200 °C. All heating and cooling steps were carried out with a rate of 10 °C/min. The softening point of materials was evaluated using Vicat test (VST), according to ISO 306_A120. The heat deflection temperature (HDT) was determined using method A with a flexural stress of 1.80 MPa, in accordance with ISO 75. Both HDT e VST tests were carried out with Amsler Allround heat deflection tester by Zwick/Roell. Fracture surface morphologies were studied using scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM Mira3 by Tescan) equipped with an Octane Elect Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) System by EDAX (AMETEK GmbH). All specimens were sputter-coated with gold before the analysis. The particle size distribution (PSD) of WS and RS was determined using a Microtrac Sync laser diffraction analyzer (Verder Scientific S.r.l.). Analyses were carried out in dry mode, with a dispersion pressure set at 100 kPa and a suction pressure of 70 kPa. The PSD results are expressed in terms of percentile values: D10, D50, and D90. Specifically, D10 indicates the particle diameter below which 10% of the sample (by mass or volume) is smaller; D50 refers to the median particle size, meaning that 50% of the particles are smaller; and D90 corresponds to the diameter below which 90% of the particles fall.

Aerobic biodegradability was evaluated following ISO 14855-1. Bioplastics (Neat, Ext 1 and Ext 8) were mixed with mature compost (1:10 TS ratio, 50% moisture) in 1-L reactors and incubated at 58 °C for 180 days. Biodegradation was assessed monitoring CO₂ production with an infrared gas analyzer. Blank tests were conducted to measure the residual CO₂ production of compost. Cellulose control tests were conducted to ensure experimental validity. Residual bioplastics were sampled from the reactors

after 1 and 3 months of degradation and subjected to TGA to monitor potential changes in the polymeric matrix.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The disposable material adopted in this study was analyzed using thermal analysis techniques to identify the polymer components. PLA was identified based on the presence of a glass transition temperature (T_g) at 49.1 °C, a melting peak (T_m) at 160.3 °C [24], and a crystallization peak (T_c) at 100.5 °C [25], while PBS was recognized by its T_m of 111.4 °C [26]. The T_g observed for PLA is lower than the values typically reported in the literature [27]. Thermogravimetric analysis revealed a main degradation peak at 347.7 °C [28], characteristic of PLA, and a second, less intense peak around 400 °C, associated with PBS [29]. Since the PLA degradation peak is more prominent than that of PBS, it can be inferred that PLA is the predominant component in the blend, accounting for around 50%. A residue of about 27.9% was measured at 800 °C. To evaluate the nature of the inorganic filler, the pellet was dissolved in chloroform and the residue was analyzed by EDS, which revealed the presence of talc and titanium dioxide. The former is typically used as a nucleating agent [30], while the latter is added to enhance the stability of polymer blends [31]. Subsequently, the polymer blend was reprocessed through eight extrusion/injection cycles. Thermal analysis results for samples 1, 6, and 8, as well as for composites containing wheat and rice straw, are reported in Table 1. TGA results revealed a shift both in the PLA degradation peak and in the temperature at 50% weight loss ($T_{50\%}$), decreasing from 346.6 °C to 343.3 °C and from 347.5 °C to 344.9 °C between Ext 1 and Ext 8, respectively. This trend is attributed to thermo-mechanical degradation and polymer chain scission occurring during repeated reprocessing cycles [11]. PBS, on the other hand, appeared unaffected by reprocessing.

While reprocessing did not significantly influence the blend's onset degradation temperature ($T_{5\%}$), the incorporation of agricultural waste caused a reduction in this parameter: 277.2 °C for wheat straw and 271.7 °C for rice straw. Similarly, the main degradation peak associated with PLA decreased to 323.2 °C for wheat straw and 324.4 °C for rice straw. This is attributed to the partial replacement of the more thermally stable polymer matrix with hemicellulose and cellulose components from wheat and rice straw, which are less thermally stable. This behavior is consistent with the findings reported by Eustathios Petinakis et al. [32], where increasing filler content leads to a reduction in PLA degradation temperature. DSC analysis did not show any significant changes in thermogram trends of the blend after reprocessing, likely due to the presence of titanium dioxide, which limits PLA chain mobility and contributes to thermal stability [33]. Furthermore, the incorporation of wheat and rice straw did not significantly affect the characteristic thermal transitions, in agreement with the results reported by Morreale et al. [34], who observed that natural fillers do not markedly influence the thermal behavior of biodegradable polymer matrices.

Sample	$T_{5\%}$ (°C)	$T_{50\%}$ (°C)	$T_{\max \text{ degradation}}$ (°C)
<i>Ext 1</i>	281.4	347.5	346.6
<i>Ext 6</i>	282.9	346	344.6
<i>Ext 8</i>	281.2	344.9	343.3
<i>Ext 8 + 10%WS</i>	277.2	337.4	323.2
<i>Ext 8 + 10%RS</i>	271.7	328.7	324.4

Table 1: TGA results of reprocessed polymer blend and composites.

Tensile and flexural quasi-static tests were conducted on both the reprocessed polymer blend and composites, and the findings are reported in Table 2.

It can be observed that reprocessing does not significantly affect the mechanical properties of the blend, either in terms of flexural or tensile behavior. This can be attributed to the presence of titania, as the literature reports the ability of titania to form bonds with the carboxylic groups of PLA [35]. The presumed reduction in PLA molecular weight due to reprocessing is expected to increase the number of terminal carboxylic groups available for interaction with the titania surface. Such enhanced interfacial interactions between the PLA matrix and the filler may contribute to mitigating the decline in mechanical

properties associated with PLA degradation [11]. As a result, it progressively reinforces the polymer matrix more effectively.

The addition of 10 wt.% of rice and wheat straw leads to an increase in both flexural and elastic moduli, accompanied by a decrease in maximum flexural and tensile strength. This behavior is attributed to the poor interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the matrix, as can be observed in the representative SEM micrograph (Figure 1). Particle size analysis revealed that the particle dimensions of RS are larger than those of WS by approximately 57.7%, 36.7%, and 44.8%, corresponding to the cumulative distribution percentiles D10, D50, and D90, respectively. As a result, the higher specific surface area of wheat straw contributes to increased matrix stiffness, as further supported by Berthet et al. [36]

Figure 1: SEM micrograph of Ext 8 with 10 wt.% of WS.

Sample	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)
<i>Ext 1</i>	42.0 (± 0.5)	3.0 (± 0.2)	62.0 (± 0.4)	6.1 (± 0.7)
<i>Ext 6</i>	42.6 (± 0.8)	3.2 (± 0.1)	65.4 (± 0.5)	6.2 (± 0.2)
<i>Ext 8</i>	43.9 (± 0.2)	3.3 (± 0.1)	64.8 (± 0.5)	6.1 (± 0.1)
<i>Ext 8 + 10%WS</i>	34.4 (± 0.8)	7.3 (± 0.5)	46.5 (± 1.8)	6.5 (± 0.4)
<i>Ext 8 + 10%RS</i>	29.7 (± 2.6)	7.0 (± 0.7)	36.4 (± 4.3)	5.8 (± 0.7)

Table 2: quasi-static mechanical tests results.

The effect of reprocessing cycles was also assessed through Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT) and Vicat Softening Temperature (VST) tests. In the HDT test, the sample is subjected to bending under a specified load, whereas in the VST test, the sample undergoes penetration by a standard indenter. The results are reported in Table 3.

Sample	HDT (°C)	VST (°C)
<i>Ext 1</i>	49.3	52.3
<i>Ext 6</i>	49.5	53.8
<i>Ext 8</i>	49.4	53.5
<i>Ext 8 + 10%WS</i>	50.9	54.5
<i>Ext 8 + 10%RS</i>	49.1	56.6

Table 3: HDT and VST results.

The HDT and VST results are consistent with those obtained from quasi-static mechanical tests, confirming that the addition of natural fillers contributes to an enhancement of the stiffness of the final composites [37, 38].

Biodegradation tests revealed that reprocessing had no significant impact on the biodegradability of the polymer blend. All the tested samples exhibited a comparable biogas evolution in terms of kinetics and yields achieving a biodegradation degree in the range 72 – 76% in 180 days. TGA indicated a preferential degradation of PLA, which was no longer detectable in the bioplastic samples after 1 and 3 months of testing. After four months testing, residual bioplastic particles were no longer visually detectable, but based on the biodegradation degree attained, it can be reasonably concluded that PBS was not fully degraded. In contrast, the addition of natural fillers in the composites led to an increased degradation rate. This behavior can be attributed to the superior hydrophilicity of the composites, which facilitates water uptake, the promotion of microbial colonization on the fibrous surface, and the intrinsic biodegradability of the lignocellulosic fillers, which degrade more readily under composting conditions [39, 40].

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the thermal, morphological, and mechanical behavior of a post-consumer biodegradable polymer blend. Reprocessing led to a slight reduction in PLA thermal stability due to thermo-mechanical degradation, with minimal effect on PBS. Despite this, mechanical performance remained stable, likely due to a better dispersion of inorganic fillers over cycles. The incorporation of wheat and rice straw slightly reduced the onset degradation temperature but did not significantly affect DSC results, indicating that natural fillers had limited impact on the blend's thermal behavior. Mechanical tests showed increased stiffness but reduced strength, due to weak matrix-filler adhesion. Wheat straw showed better performance compared to rice straw, possibly due to its higher cellulose content and smaller fiber dimensions. Overall, the results highlight the potential of combining mechanical recycling of biodegradable polymer blends with agro-industrial residues to create composites with balanced thermal and mechanical performance while preserving their potential for compostability. Future developments should focus on improving the interfacial adhesion between the polymer matrix and natural fillers through surface treatments or compatibilizers, in order to enhance strength and toughness without compromising biodegradability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was partially funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU, Mission 4, Component 1, within the BOOMERANG project (Bio-cOmpOsite Material dEsign forpAckagiNG, CUP B53D23006530006) and partially within the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.1, Call for tender No. 104 published on February 2, 2022 by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR), funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU – Project Title CellBioReComp – CUP I53D23006560001.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Soares, I. Miguel, C. Venâncio, I. Lopes, and M. Oliveira, “Public views on plastic pollution: Knowledge, perceived impacts, and pro-environmental

- behaviours,” *J Hazard Mater*, vol. 412, p. 125227, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2021.125227.
- [2] J. Hopewell, R. Dvorak, and E. Kosior, “Plastics Recycling: Challenges and Opportunities,” *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*, vol. 364, pp. 2115–2126, May 2009, doi: 10.1098/rstb.2008.0311.
- [3] P. G. C. Nayanathara Thathsarani Pilapitiya and A. S. Ratnayake, “The world of plastic waste: A review,” *Cleaner Materials*, vol. 11, p. 100220, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.CLEMA.2024.100220.
- [4] M. H. Rahman and P. R. Bhoi, “An overview of non-biodegradable bioplastics,” *J Clean Prod*, vol. 294, p. 126218, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.126218.
- [5] D. Kasprzak, C. C. Mayorga-Martinez, and M. Pumera, “Sustainable and Flexible Energy Storage Devices: A Review,” *Energy & Fuels*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 74–97, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1021/acs.energyfuels.2c03217.
- [6] V. Kumar, R. Sehgal, and R. Gupta, “Blends and composites of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and their applications,” *Eur Polym J*, vol. 161, p. 110824, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.EURPOLYMJ.2021.110824.
- [7] R. Geyer, J. R. Jambeck, and K. L. Law, “Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made,” 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://advances.sciencemag.org/>
- [8] S. C. Teixeira, N. O. Gomes, T. V. de Oliveira, P. Fortes-Da-Silva, N. de F. F. Soares, and P. A. Raymundo-Pereira, “Review and Perspectives of sustainable, biodegradable, eco-friendly and flexible electronic devices and (Bio)sensors,” *Biosens Bioelectron X*, vol. 14, p. 100371, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOSX.2023.100371.
- [9] L. G. Pinaeva and A. S. Noskov, “Biodegradable biopolymers: Real impact to environment pollution,” *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 947, p. 174445, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2024.174445.
- [10] G. Kale, T. Kijchavengkul, R. Auras, M. Rubino, S. E. Selke, and S. P. Singh, “Compostability of bioplastic packaging materials: An overview,” Mar. 08, 2007. doi: 10.1002/mabi.200600168.
- [11] I. Bavasso *et al.*, “Recycling of a commercial biodegradable polymer blend: Influence of reprocessing cycles on rheological and thermo-mechanical properties,” *Polym Test*, vol. 134, p. 108418, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2024.108418>.
- [12] S. M. Emadian, T. T. Onay, and B. Demirel, “Biodegradation of bioplastics in natural environments,” *Waste Management*, vol. 59, pp. 526–536, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.WASMAN.2016.10.006.
- [13] A. Folino, A. Karageorgiou, P. S. Calabrò, and D. Komilis, “Biodegradation of Wasted Bioplastics in Natural and Industrial Environments: A Review,” *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 15, 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12156030.
- [14] K. Babaremu, O. P. Oladijo, and E. Akinlabi, “Biopolymers: A suitable replacement for plastics in product packaging,” Oct. 01, 2023, *KeAi Communications Co.* doi: 10.1016/j.aiepr.2023.01.001.
- [15] M. Zhang *et al.*, “Recent advances in polymers and polymer composites for food packaging,” Mar. 01, 2022, *Elsevier B.V.* doi: 10.1016/j.mattod.2022.01.022.
- [16] R. Kumar, K. Sadeghi, J. Jang, and J. Seo, “Mechanical, chemical, and bio-recycling of biodegradable plastics: A review,” *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 882, p. 163446, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.163446>.

- [17] K. Hirao, Y. Nakatsuchi, and H. Ohara, "Alcoholysis of Poly(l-lactic acid) under microwave irradiation," *Polym Degrad Stab*, vol. 95, no. 6, pp. 925–928, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.POLYMDEGRADSTAB.2010.03.027.
- [18] K. W. Meereboer, M. Misra, and A. K. Mohanty, "Review of recent advances in the biodegradability of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) bioplastics and their composites," Sep. 07, 2020, *Royal Society of Chemistry*. doi: 10.1039/d0gc01647k.
- [19] I. Zembouai, S. Bruzard, M. Kaci, A. Benhamida, Y.-M. Corre, and Y. Grohens, "Mechanical Recycling of Poly(3-Hydroxybutyrate-co-3-Hydroxyvalerate)/Polylactide Based Blends," *J Environ Polym Degrad*, vol. 22, no. 4, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s10924-014-0684.
- [20] E. Achukwu and M. Mfon Owen, "Influence of Reprocessing Cycles on the Mechanical and Morphological Properties of Recycled Polypropylene." [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356536452>
- [21] K. Manickaraj *et al.*, "Value-added utilization of agricultural wastes in biocomposite production: Characteristics and applications," *Ann N Y Acad Sci*, vol. n/a, no. n/a, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.15368>.
- [22] J. Yang, Y. C. Ching, and C. H. Chuah, "Applications of Lignocellulosic Fibers and Lignin in Bioplastics: A Review," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 11, no. 5, 2019, doi: 10.3390/polym11050751.
- [23] F. Asad, K. Immonen, T. Kiiskinen, A. Mikkelsen, and E. Sarlin, "The Impact of Mechanical Recycling on Ligno-Cellulose Fibre Containing PLA Biocomposite," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 17, no. 6, 2025, doi: 10.3390/polym17060732.
- [24] B. Tisserat, N. Joshee, A. Mahapatra, G. Selling, and V. Finkenstadt, "Physical and mechanical properties of extruded poly(lactic acid)-based *Paulownia elongata* biocomposites," *Ind Crops Prod*, vol. 44, pp. 88–96, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2012.10.030.
- [25] Y. Liu *et al.*, "Crystallization Morphology Regulation on Enhancing Heat Resistance of Polylactic Acid," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 7, 2020, doi: 10.3390/polym12071563.
- [26] T. Yokohara and M. Yamaguchi, "Structure and properties for biomass-based polyester blends of PLA and PBS," *Eur Polym J*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 677–685, Mar. 2008, doi: 10.1016/J.EURPOLYMJ.2008.01.008.
- [27] T. Zhao *et al.*, "Thermal, crystallization, and mechanical properties of polylactic acid (PLA)/poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) blends," *Polymer Bulletin*, vol. 81, no. 3, pp. 2481–2504, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00289-023-04848-9.
- [28] G. WANG and A. LI, "Thermal Decomposition and Kinetics of Mixtures of Polylactic Acid and Biomass during Copyrolysis," *Chin J Chem Eng*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 929–933, Dec. 2008, doi: 10.1016/S1004-9541(09)60018-5.
- [29] A. Anstey, S. Muniyasamy, M. M. Reddy, M. Misra, and A. Mohanty, "Processability and Biodegradability Evaluation of Composites from Poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) Bioplastic and Biofuel Co-products from Ontario," *J Polym Environ*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 209–218, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s10924-013-0633-8.
- [30] W. Zhuang, J. Liu, J. H. Zhang, B. X. Hu, and J. Shen, "Preparation, characterization, and properties of TiO₂/PLA nanocomposites by in situ polymerization," *Polym Compos*, vol. 30, no. 8, pp. 1074–1080, 2009, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.20658>.

- [31] Q. Zhang, D. Li, H. Zhang, G. Su, and G. Li, "Preparation and properties of poly(lactic acid)/sesbania gum/nano-TiO₂ composites," *Polymer Bulletin*, vol. 75, no. 2, pp. 623–635, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s00289-017-2059-2.
- [32] E. Petinakis *et al.*, "Biodegradation and thermal decomposition of poly(lactic acid)-based materials reinforced by hydrophilic fillers," *Polym Degrad Stab*, vol. 95, no. 9, pp. 1704–1707, Sep. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.POLYMDEGRADSTAB.2010.05.027.
- [33] S. Bergaliyeva *et al.*, "Thermal and Mechanical Properties of Reprocessed Polylactide/Titanium Dioxide Nanocomposites for Material Extrusion Additive Manufacturing," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 15, no. 16, 2023, doi: 10.3390/polym15163458.
- [34] M. Morreale, A. Liga, M. C. Mistretta, L. Ascione, and F. P. La Mantia, "Mechanical, Thermomechanical and Reprocessing Behavior of Green Composites from Biodegradable Polymer and Wood Flour," *Materials*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 7536–7548, 2015, doi: 10.3390/ma8115406.
- [35] H. Zhang *et al.*, "Preparation, characterization and properties of PLA/TiO₂ nanocomposites based on a novel vane extruder," *RSC Adv.*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 4639–4647, 2015, doi: 10.1039/C4RA14538K.
- [36] M. A. Berthet, H. Angellier-Coussy, V. Chea, V. Guillard, E. Gastaldi, and N. Gontard, "Sustainable food packaging: Valorising wheat straw fibres for tuning PHBV-based composites properties," *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf*, vol. 72, pp. 139–147, May 2015, doi: 10.1016/J.COMPOSITESA.2015.02.006.
- [37] S. Yaisun and T. Trongsatitkul, "PLA-Based Hybrid Biocomposites: Effects of Fiber Type, Fiber Content, and Annealing on Thermal and Mechanical Properties," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 15, no. 20, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.3390/polym15204106.
- [38] F. A. Rabbani *et al.*, "Lignocellulosic fiber reinforcement in PPRC composites: An analysis of structural and thermal enhancements," *PLoS One*, vol. 19, no. 11 November, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0309128.
- [39] A. Quitadamo, V. Massardier, V. Iovine, A. Belhadj, R. Bayard, and M. Valente, "Effect of Cellulosic Waste Derived Filler on the Biodegradation and Thermal Properties of HDPE and PLA Composites," *Processes*, vol. 7, no. 10, 2019, doi: 10.3390/pr7100647.
- [40] A. Kozłowska, K. Gorący, and M. El Fray, "Biodegradable Polymer Composites Based on Poly(butylene succinate) Copolyesters and Wood Flour," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 17, no. 7, 2025, doi: 10.3390/polym17070883.